

**A PHARMACO-CLINICAL STUDY OF MAJUPHAL AND KANKOL W.S.R. TO THEIR
EFFECT ON SHWETA PRADAR**

Dr. Savita Prajapati*, Dr. Anjali Jain, Dr. Basanti Guru

¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of Dravyaguna, Veena Vadini Ayurveda College Bhopal MP.

²Assistant Professor Dept. of Dravyaguna, Pt Khushilal Sharma Govt (Auto) Ayurveda College and Institute Bhopal MP.

³Professor and HOD Dept. of Prasutitantra and Strirog, Pt Khushilal Sharma Govt (Auto) Ayurveda College and Institute Bhopal MP.

***Corresponding Author: Dr. Savita Prajapati**

Assistant Professor, Dept. of Dravyaguna, Veena Vadini Ayurveda College Bhopal MP.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17275231>

Article Received on 13/08/2025

Article Revised on 03/09/2025

Article Accepted on 24/09/2025

ABSTRACT

The study was conducted on total 60 patients, in which 52 patients have completed the treatment. It is a comparative randomized clinical study of *Majuphala* and *Kankola* churna on *Shweta pradara* disease. Leucorrhoea occurs commonly among weak and anemic women. Among young female it may be due to threadworm, inflammation of the womb following childbirth, as the result of general debility combined with lack of cleanliness or infections and also liable to cause much mental stress, problem of sexual anxiety and even sometimes failure to conceive. *Majuphala* is expected to disintegrate the pathogenesis of *shwetapradar* due to its *Kashaya Rasa*, *Laghu*, *Ruksha Guna*, *Sheeta Virya* and *Katu vipaka*. Further, it has *Kapha Pitta Shamaka*, and *Stambhaka* properties. *Kankola* has been widely used in *mukh rogas*, *yonigata roga*, *kapha vata har agnimandya*, *daurgandhahar*. Conclusion of study found that *Majuphal* showed better percentage of relief on some DLC parameter as compared to *Kankol*.

INTRODUCTION

“A Pharmacological Study of *Majuphal* and *Kankol* W.S.R. to their effect on *Shweta Pradar*”. The word ‘Dravyaguna’ means the science dealing with properties and actions of drugs. At first, to understand the fundamentals of Ayurveda in general before one can grasp the concepts of Dravyaguna. Panchabhutas (Akasha, Vayu, Agni, Jala and Prithivi) are regarded as physico-chemical basis of the material objects. When life evolved, out of these five, three came forward to control and regulate the biological functions. These three (Vata, Pitta, Kapha) are known as tridhatu (tridosha in pathological state) having specific functions of Vikshepa, Adana, and Visarga respectively. Primarily based on this fundamental background, the following concepts were developed to explain the drug action.

Dravya (Substance-drug & diet), Guna (Property), Rasa (Taste), Vipaka (Final transformation), Virya (Potency), Prabhava (Specific potency), Karma (Action). ‘Dravya’ means drug in this context. Acharya Charaka has classified drugs from various angles, according to source, effect on doshas, composition, properties, actions, etc. Marvelous piece in the Charaka-Samhita is the description of fifty groups of drugs according to their main action. Similar classification is found in the

Sushruta-Samhita where thirty-seven groups of drugs are defined according to their effect and therapeutic uses.

The acceptability of alternative medicine particularly the herbal medicine has now become a critical need of time. It is the time when Ayurvedic concept should be proved on parameters. Scholar has needed to find out a safe, effective, easily available and cost effective drug hence these drugs are being undertaken for present research to see their efficacy in *shweta pradara*.

Drug Review:- *Majuphala* is expected to disintegrate the pathogenesis of *shwetapradar* due to its *Kashaya Rasa*, *Laghu*, *Ruksha Guna*, *Sheeta Virya* and *Katu vipaka*. Further, it has *Kapha Pitta Shamaka*, and *Stambhaka* properties. *Kankola* was identified and used as a medicine from samhita period. There are lots of reference are available in samhitas. *Kankola* has been widely used in *mukh rogas*, *yonigata roga*, *kapha vata har agnimandya*, *daurgandhahar*. Most of the acharyas have explained *kankol* elaborately. Many properties and therapeutic uses are described by them.

Disease Review:- All women have experienced some short of vaginal discharge in her life span. *Ayurveda* considers that Leucorrhoea is caused by the vitiation of

Kapha; all gynecological disorders come under the heading of *Yonivyapad*. No any description of *Shweta pradar* has been described by scholars of *Brihatrayee* for abnormal white discharges. The word *Shweta pradar* has been described in texts during and after medieval period. It occurs commonly among weak and anemic women. It can also be due to the inflammation of the womb following childbirth. Among young female it may be due to threadworm, as the result of general debility combined with lack of cleanliness or infections.

In modern science white discharge from the vagina is called as Leucorrhoea. Normally, vaginal discharge occurs in regular variations of amount and consistency during the course of the menstrual cycle. A greater than usual amount is normal in pregnancy, and a decrease is to be expected after delivery, during lactation, and after menopause. It may be physiological or pathological. Physiological excess of vaginal discharge does not require any treatment. But, the pathological conditions which necessitate treatment. Although Leucorrhoea does not causes mortality but morbidity is associated with this. The complaint is liable to cause much mental stress, problem of sexual anxiety and even sometimes failure to conceive. Apart from this, it also causes local inconvenience to the patient.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To assess the “A *pharmaco-clinical study of Majuphal and Kankol w.s.r. to their effect on shweta pradar*” was carried out. For this study scholar has taken two drug Majuphal churn and Kankola churn administered along with jala, considering their efficacy in shweta pradar.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

In this present clinical study patients of shweta pradar with confirm diagnosis were taken randomly from the OPD section of department of *prasuti tantra and stri roga*, Pt. Khusilal Sharma Govt. (Auto) Ayurveda College and Institute, Bhopal M.P. The present study was planned with the followings aims and objectives-

1. To evaluate the pharmacological efficacy of both drug *Majuphal and Kankola* in the management of *Shweta Pradar*.
2. To compare the efficacy of both drug (*Majuphal and Kankola*) in *Shweta Pradar*.

Drugs: - The raw drugs *Majuphala* and *Kankola* were obtained and prepared at of *Ras-shastra and bhaishajya kalpana* department of pt.khushilal Sharma Govt. (Auto) Ayurveda college and institute, Bhopal (M.P.).

Study design: - The study was conducted on total 60 patients, in which 52 patients have completed the treatment and remaining 8 patients were dropout. It is a comparative randomized clinical study of *Majuphala* and *Kankola* churna on *shweta pradar* disease in women with pre- test and post- test design, a special proforma was prepared with all point of history taking, physical

sign and lab investigations included. The selected patients were categorized in two groups. The parameters of sign and symptoms were scored on the basis of standard method of statistical analysis.

Duration and method of administration of the drug

1. Majuphal churn 1.5gm BD with plain water orally.
2. Kankola churn 1.5gm BD with plain water orally.

Interventions

- The patients were assessed before and after treatment as per assessment criteria.
- The nature of the study was explained to the patients in detailed and pre treatment consent was taken.
- The patients had full rights to withdraw from the study at any time.

Criteria for selection of patient

Inclusion criteria

- Married women.
- Excessive vaginal white/yellowish discharge with and without other associated symptoms like *Yoni Kandu, Yoni Daurgandh, Katishool, Yonidah, Daurbalya, Adho-udar vedana*

Exclusion criteria

- Unmarried women.
- Pregnant women and lactating mother.
- Any other chronic illness like – carcinoma of cervix, uterine fibroid, vaginal
- Polyp, chronic pelvic inflammatory diseases cervical erosion.

Criteria for diagnosis

- Patients having the complaints of excessive white/yellowish discharge per vagina associated with or without other symptoms like *Yonikandu, Yoni daurgandh, Katishool, Yonidaah, Daurbalya, Adho-udar vedana*.
- Patient will be examined thoroughly both symptomatically and clinically (per vaginal and speculum examination).

Investigation

- Routine pathology investigation of hematology – CBC with ESR.
- Pap smear test (if required).
- Microscopic examination of wet vaginal smear test.

Assessment criteria

The efficacy of *Majuphal (quercus infectoria oliv.)* and *Kankola (piper cubeba Linn.)* on *Shweta Pradar* were assessed on the basis of subjective and objective parameters before and after treatment. Criteria of assessment of results were set aside on the basis of relief in the sign and symptoms of shweta pradar. For this purpose, scores were given in following scoring patterns.

Symptoms wise grading pattern

Symptoms	Grade 0	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3
Yonigata shweta/ Pitabh sraav	No discharge	Frequent excessive vaginal discharge	Moderate discharge (Soiling undergarments)	Severe excessive vaginal discharge (Pt needs to use pads)
Yonikandu (Vulval itching)	No itching	Mild itching (itching urges occassionly)	Moderate Itching (itching urges continuously)	Severe itching (Making patients irritable with ulceration in vulva & vagina)
Yonidaurgandha (Foul smell)	Non offensive	Mild (Occasional/Periodic bad smell)	Moderate (continuous bad smell throught the month)	Severe (Continuous foul smell)
Yoni vedana	Absent	Mild pain (Only feeling of discomfort)	Moderate (Occasional pain)	Severe (Continuous pain)
Katishool (Backache)	Absent	Mild pain (on and off slight pain)	Moderate pain (pain during work)	Severe pain (continuous pain)
Daurbalya	no weekness	Mild (patients is able to involve in routine activity)	Moderate (Patients is slow to involve in routine activity)	Severe (patients feel exhausted to involve in routine activity)
Adho udar Vedana	Absent	Mild pain (only feeling of discomfort)	Moderate (occasional pain)	Severe (continuous pain)
Yoni daha	Absent	Mild (feeling of burning sensation, no need of medicine)	Moderate (Disturbs daily routine, need of medicine and relief after medicine)	Severe (Continuous daha)

Objective criteria: Assessment of the therapy was also carried out by comparing before and after treatment values of hematological and Microscopic examination of wet vaginal smear test.

Criteria for the assessment of overall effect of the therapy

To evaluate this, total scores of patients observed before treatment (B.T.) and after treatment (A.T.). Average of respective scores is calculated and then percentage of change / improvement is calculated by following formula:

$$\frac{\text{Average BT} - \text{Average AT} \times 100}{\text{Average BT}}$$

Overall effect of therapy was assesses in term of-

Complete remission	100% relief
Marked improvement	>75-<100% relief
Moderate improvement	>50-<75% relief
Mild improvement	>25-<50% relief
Unchanged	<25% relief

Hypothesis

Null-hypothesis: - H_0 : The effect of *Majuphal* and *Kankola churna* on *Shweta Pradar* are equal.

Alternative hypothesis: - H_1

(a): *Majuphal churn* will more effective than *kankola* on *shweta pradar*.

(b): *Kankola churn* will more effective than *Majuphal* on *shweta pradar*.

STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF RESULTS**1- Statistical assessment of results for subjective criteria**

- **Wilcoxon signed rank test:-** This non parametric statistical hypothesis test was applied to assess the effect of therapy in related samples for repeated measurements on a single group sample.
- **Mann-whitney rank sum test:-** This test was applied to compare the effect of therapies of both groups having categorical and unpaired data. The obtained reports were subjected to the following suitable statistical analysis.

After preparing the master chart of all the data in m.s.excel worksheet, statistical calculations were done with the help of graph pad instat 3 software.

2. Statistical assessment of results for objective criteria

- To assess the effect of drugs on objective criteria in each group paired 'T' test was used.
- To compare between both groups was done by using unpaired 'T' test for objective criteria after treatment.

Statistical estimation of results:-The obtained results were interpreted as per the level of significance. $P < 0.001$ considered as extremely significant.

P<0.005 considered as very significant.
 P<0.05 considered as significant.
 P>0.05 considered as not significant.

Follow up: Patients were advised to report after one month completion of course.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

The observation and result of the clinical study are given below in tabular form.

	Number of patient		Total patient
	Group A	Group B	
Registered	30	30	60
Completed	28	24	52
Dropout	2	6	8

Total observation data divided into 3 sections for better understanding

- Demographic data
- Data related to disease
- Data related to response to the treatment (results)

S. N.	Demographic Parameter	Percentage of patients (%)
1.	Age (20-30) yrs	38.33
2.	Religion	81.66
3.	Family (Nuclear)	71.66
4.	Socio-economic status (middle)	61.66
5.	Education (Primary School)	35
6.	Marital status (Married)	100
7.	Habitat (Urban)	71.66
8.	Occupation (Houseife)	70
9.	Disease onset (Gradual)	80
10.	Past medical history (Absent)	83.33
11.	Past treatment history (None)	83.33
12.	Family history (Absent)	83.33
13.	Diet (Vegetarian)	71.66
14.	Dominant Rasahar (Madhur)	31.66
15.	Appetite (Moderate)	53.33
16.	Agni (Sama)	53.33
17.	Koshtha (Madhyam)	61.66
18.	Abhishyandi ahaar (No)	66.66
19.	Adhyasana (No)	80
20.	Viruddha ahara (No)	63.33
21.	Addiction (Tea)	83.33
22.	Nature of sleep (Samyaka)	51.66
23.	Emotional makeup (Normal)	63.33
24.	Age of menarche (13-15yr)	58.33

GRAPHS OF OBSERVATION

RESULT

The subjective and objective parameters of patients of each group were examined according to the clinical

findings and the results were analysed from the statistical analysis.

Group A

S.n	Symptoms	Mean			% Relief	SD	SE	p-value	Result
		BT	AT	Diff.					
1	Yonigata shweta Srava	1.536	0.2143	1.321	86.0026	0.5480	0.1036	P<0.0001	E.S
2	Yonikandu	0.6786	0.1429	0.5357	78.941	0.6929	0.1310	P=0.0002	E.S
3	Yonidaurgandh	0.4643	0.03571	0.4286	92.311	0.6901	0.1304	P=0.0039	V.S
4	Yoni vedana	0.2857	0.1429	0.1429	50.017	0.4484	0.08474	P=0.2500	N.S
5	Katishool	1.036	0.6429	0.3929	37.924	0.6289	0.1188	P=0.0039	V.S
6	Daurbalya	0.9286	0.7857	0.1429	15.388	0.3563	0.06734	P=0.1250	N.S
7	Adho-udar vedana	0.7857	0.3929	0.3929	50.006	0.6853	0.1295	P=0.0078	V.S
8	Yoni daha	0.2857	0.1071	0.1786	62.513	0.3900	0.07371	P=0.0625	N.S

Group B

S.n	Symptoms	Mean			% Relief	SD	SE	p-value	Result
		BT	AT	Diff.					
1	Yonigata shweta Srava	1.750	0.3750	1.375	86.0026	.5480	0.1036	P<0.0001	E.S
2	Yonikandu	0.7917	0.2500	0.5417	68.422	0.5882	0.1201	P=0.0005	E.S
3	Yonidaurgandh	0.3333	0.08333	0.2500	75.007	0.4423	0.09029	P=0.313	S
4	Yoni vedana	0.08333	0.04167	0.0167	20.04	0.2041	0.04167	p>0.99	N.S
5	Katishool	1.917	1.375	0.5417	28.22	0.7211	0.1472	P=0.0010	E.S
6	Daurbalya	0.9167	0.7500	0.1667	18.184	0.3807	0.07771	P=0.1250	N.S
7	Adho-udar vedana	1.292	0.7083	0.5833	45.147	0.7755	0.1583	P=0.078	V.S
8	Yoni daha	0.2500	0.08333	0.1667	66.68	0.4815	0.09829	P=0.2500	N.S

Showing the pattern of result in all objective parameters of Group A

Test	Mean			% of Relief	±SD	S.E.	P-value	Result
	B.T.	A.T.	D					
Hb%	11.004	11.896	-0.8929	8.114	1.640	.3100	0.0077	V.S.
TLC	7692.9	7403.6	289.29	3.760	1782.1	336.78	0.3979	N.S.
ESR	19.821	14.214	5.607	28.288	6.500	1.228	0.0001	E.S.
DLC-N	56.929	60.000	-3.071	-5.3944	9.641	1.822	0.0517	N.S.
L	39	35.321	3.679	9.4333	9.783	1.849	0.0284	S.
M	1.607	2.071	-0.4643	-28.892	0.8381	0.1584	0.0034	V.S.
E	1.821	2.643	-0.8214	-45.10	1.278	0.2415	0.0011	V.S.
B	000	00	00	00	00	00	00	N.S.
Pus cells	10.536	2.393	8.143	77.287	5.082	0.9605	P<0.0001	E.S.
Epithelial cells	8.393	2.357	6.036	71.917	3.564	0.6735	P<0.0001	E.S.
Trichomonas vaginalis	0.07143	0.00	0.07143	100	0.2623	0.04956	P=0.1610	N.S.
Candida albicans	0.0713	0.00	0.0713	100	0.2623	0.04956	0.1610	N.S.
Bacteria	2.964	0.2143	2.750	92.780	3.668	0.6932	0.0002	E.S.

Showing the pattern of result in all objective parameters of Group B

Test	Mean			% of Relief	±SD	S.E.	P-value	Result
	B.T.	A.T.	D					
Hb%	11.800	11.567	0.2333	1.9771	1.174	0.2396	0.1701	N.S.
TLC	7833.3	8175	-341.67	-4.361	2448.8	499.85	0.2505	N.S.
ESR	16.083	15.708	0.3750	2.331	7.051	1.439	0.3984	N.S.
DLC-N	60.125	59.542	0.5833	0.9701	12.918	2.637	0.4134	N.S.
L	34.750	36.708	-1.958	-5.634	14.412	2.942	0.2561	N.S.
M	2.292	2.250	0.04167	1.818	0.9991	0.2039	0.8399	N.S.
E	3.042	2.958	0.0833	2.738	1.316	0.2686	0.3796	N.S.
B	000	00	00	00	00	00	00	N.S.
Pus cells	11.167	3.333	7.833	70.144	5.700	1.164	0.0001	E.S.
Epithelial cells	8.375	3.000	5.375	64.179	4.994	1.019	P<0.0001	E.S.
Trichomonas vaginalis	0.1250	0.000	0.1250	100	0.4484	0.09153	P=0.1853	N.S.
Candida albicans	0.2083	0.1250	0.0833	39.990	0.2823	0.05763	0.0808	N.S.
Bacteria	0.2917	000	0.2917	100	0.6241	0.1274	0.0158	S.

Percentage of relief on all subjective parameters

Lakshana	% of Relief in Group A	% of Relief in Group B
Yonisrava	86.0026	78.5714
Associated symptoms		
Yonikandu	78.941	68.422
Yonidurgandha	92.311	75.007
Yonivedna	50.017	20.040
Katishool	37.924	28.22
Daurbalya	15.388	18.184
Adho udar vedna	50.006	45.147
Yoni dah	62.513	66.68

Percentage of relief on all objective parameters

Test	% of Relief in Group A	% of Relief in Group B	
HB%	8.114	1.9771	
TLC	3.760	-4.361	
ESR	28.288	2.331	
DLC-N	-5.3944	0.9701	
L	9.4333	-5.634	
M	-28.892	1.818	
E	-45.10	2.738	
B	00	00	
Wet vaginal smear test microscopic examination	Pus cells	77.287	70.144
	Epithelial cell	71.917	64.179
	Trichomonas vaginalis	100	100
	Candida albicans	100	39.990
	Bacteria	92.780	100

Overall Percentage of improvement of 52 patients

Improvement Status	Group A		Group B	
	No of patients	% of patients	No of patients	% of patients
Complete remission	1	3.57	3	12.50
Marked Improvement	6	21.42	4	16.66
Moderate Improvement	11	39.28	7	29.16
Mild Improvement	5	17.85	8	33.33
Unchanged	5	17.85	2	8.33

DISCUSSION

The present study entitled “A *pharmaco-clinical study of Majuphal and Kankol w.s.r. to their effect on shweta pradar*” was planned to assess the pharmacological efficacy of Majuphal and Kankol in sweta pradar.

Action of Majuphal:- Majuphala has kasaya rasa, Laghu and ruksha guna, sheeta veerya and akatu vipaka. And kaphapittahar by which it breaks the samprapti. Majuphala has kasaya rasa which is a combination of vayu and prithvi mahabhoota. Vayu is laghu, ruksha and khara in quality which dries up the excessive fluids. Due to kapha pitta shamak, stambhan, vishaghna, and kaphaghna property of kasaya ras, it pacifies vitiated kapha and kleda. (c.su.26/11;4,42;6)

And prithvi mahabhoota by virtue of kathina, khara and sthira in quality oppose to drava and sara guna and reduces the srava. These two mahabhoota are having quality opposite to kapha.(c.su.26/11;1). Laghu guna subside kapha dosa and clears the channels of the body (srotosodhan) by virtue of agni, vayu and akash mahabhoota and ruksha guna dries up the excessive fluids. Katu vipaka and sheeta veerya of majuphala, pacify vitiated vata and kapha and reduces the srava due to its visyandan property of sheeta veerya.

Action of drug majuphal can be understood as: Yoni sodhan- cleans the vagina by sodhan and vranropana property. Kill causative micro-organism- by krimighna,

kandughna, and vishaghna property. Rejuvenate the epithelium- by balyavardhak property.

Action as per modern pharmacological activities: Majuphal has analgesic, antibacterial, anti carcinogenic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, larvicidal, wound healing pharmacological property by which it kill causative micro-organism and treat the sweta pradar.^[1]

Kankola: Kankola has katu and tikta ras. Katu rasa is a combination of vayu and agni mahabhoota and tikta rasa is a combination of vayu and akash mahabhoota. Vayu is laghu, ruksha and khara in quality which dries up the excessive fluids. Katu rasa subside pichhila and gurutwa guna of kapha. And tikta rasa pacify vitiated kapha and kleda. On the other hand tikta rasa also having kandughna, krimighna, kleda and kaphasoshan property and causes ama pachan, direct inhibit the growth of krimi as well as reduces shotha and finally diminishes srava. (Ch.Su 26/43-5).

Laghu and tikshna guna of kankola subside kapha dosha and clears the channels of the body (srotosodhana) and ruksha guna creates kharta in body and reduces the kleda of body and tikshna guna. Katu vipaka and ushna veerya of kankola pacify vitiated vata and kapha and stimulate agni. So because of their agnivardhak property they increase digestive power which digests amarasa and reduces the excessive production of kapha and removes the obstruction of the srotasas.

Action of drug: Kill causative micro-organism- by its vishnasak property and sotha hara property. It is a ingredient of femilin tablet^[2] (ayurvedic medicin) which treat the vaginitis, trichomonas vaginitis, gonococcal infection Leucorrhoea etc. Sweta pradar is kapha vata dosa predominant tridoshaja vyadhi and the trial drug kankola also has tridoshatmaka specially kapha vata dosa hara properties.

Action as per modern pharmacological activities:^[3] The modern technology has proved that drug kankol (piper cubeba linn.) has Antimicrobial, Antifungal, Antioxidant activity, Nephroprotective, Hepatoprotective, and Antibacterial pharmacological properties by which it kill the causative micro-organism and also support the vaginal defense mechanism.

Discussion on disease review: *Shwetapradar* (Vaginal discharge) in the reproductive age group is the most common complaint encountered everyday both by gynecologists and general practitioners. Due to today's food habits, changing life style vaginal discharge has emerged out as one of the commonest reproductive health problem of women. Regarding the gravity of the disease, it does not cause mortality but morbidity is associated with this. It also causes mental stress, local inconvenience to the patient which deteriorates the day to day work and the quality of life. Thus it does not cut the years of life but the life of the years.

Shwetapradar is not mentioned as a separate clinical entity in classics, but it can be considered as a symptom in many *Stree Roga*. Mostly all Aacharyas described white vaginal discharge as *Shwetapradar*. However, the word "*Shwetapradar*" was firstly mentioned by Acharya Vrinda Madhava on 9th century A.D. Later on Commentator Chakrapani has explained (Cha. Chi.30/116, Chakra -Commentary), but he had described in very brief.

In the present study the patients were having the history of intake of *kapha vardhak ahara*. *Mithya vihara* produces the *sthanika uttejna* in the *yonis* which ultimately results in the vitiation of *sthanika doshas*. Leads to *sweta pradar*. In present study patients were having the history of madhura rasa and lanvan rasa predominant ahar.

Artava vradhhi and artav kshaya and along with hormonal imbalance can be included. In the present study patients were having the history of dysmenorrhoea, scanty bleeding. Unknown or idiopathic factor comes under this category causes may be Daivakrut or purva janma kruta karma. The complete vyakta lakshanas are considered as rupa. Pratyatma lakshana of sweta pradar is yonigata excessive shweta/yellow srava. In the present study all the patients were having the complaints of excessive yonigat shweta/yellow srava. Most of the patients were having some others associated complaints

like yonikandu, yonivedana, katishoola, daurbalya, adho-udar vedana and yonidah etc.

Due to *Nidana Sevana* (*Aharaja Nidanas* like excessive intake of *Madhura rasa* etc., *Viharaja Nidana* like *Vegavidharana*, *Ati vyavaya*, *diwaswapna* etc.) *Doshas* mainly *Vata* and *Kapha* become vitiated. Vitiated *Doshas* caused *Manda Jatharagni* and eventually formed undigested material i.e. *Ama* commences to accumulate in the *Amashaya*. The accumulated *Ama* vitiates the first rasa *Dhatu*, which is coming in contact throughout the body (*Prakopavastha*) through *Rasavaha Srotasa*, which leads to *Rasavaha Srotodushti* followed by *Artavaha Sroto Dushti* and finally vitiating the *Yoni*. Due to *Yoni dushti* there is *Yonigata Srava* known as *Shwetapradar*. While studying the various conditions in which *Shwetapradar* is described, *Kapha* can be considered as main causative *Dosha* by its vitiated *Snigdha* and *Pichchhila* properties.

Kapha & *Vata* seem to be leading *Doshas* responsible for *Shwetapradar* but the role of *Pitta* cannot totally be neglected because it is responsible for Paka. Most of the vaginal discharge is the consequence of urogenital infections. In present study patients were also having the complaints of yoni daah and mutra daah, so sweta pradar can be considered as vata kapha pradhan tridosaja vyadhi.

Discussion on clinical study

The clinical study was carried out on 60 patients of sweta pradar which were divided into two group. Patients of group1 were administered with Majuphala churna 1½ - 1½ gm twice daily with a jala orally. And patients of group2 were administered with kankola churna 1½ -1½ gm twice daily with a jala orally. The patients were selected randomly irrespective of age, sex, religion etc. each patients was thoroughly examined on the basis of dually prepared research proforma. discussion on their observation and results are following.

Discussion on observation of demographic profile

- **Age:** The present study found that maximum 38.33% patients belonged to the age group of 20-30 years. & 36.66% patients belonged to the 31-40 years. Vaginal infection and discharge commonly occur in women of reproductive age.
- **Religion:** The present study found that maximum 81.66% were Hindu, and 15% Muslim patients were registered. This data may be found due to geographical dominance of Hindu people in this region.
- **Socioeconomic status:** In this study 61.66% of patients were belonging to middle class and 11.66% in very poor class. Due to excessive hard work, malnutrition, mental and physical strain and stress etc. plays major role in provoking the disease.
- **Educational status:** In the present study we found that maximum 35% patients were primary class educated while 6.66% patients were educated up to

post graduation. It suggests that still less education is found in female in our society. This clearly indicates the lack of knowledge about personal hygiene among less educated people. Finally land up into a serious health hazard like vaginal discharge and vaginal infection.

- **Marital status:** In the present study we found that maximum 100% patients were married. In randomized clinical trial study only married patients were selected in both groups because general gynecological examination could not be done on unmarried patients. Other reasons were that after marriage reproductive tract infection most frequently seen in married women.
- **Region:** In the present study we found that highest prevalence was seen in urban areas (71.66%) followed by rural community (28.33%). due to unhygienic condition or may be fast food women more prone to produce excessive white vaginal discharge.
- **Occupational:** In the present study we found that maximum 70% patients were housewives and 16.66% patients were labour. These data reflect that our society still does not allow women to go outside for work even if economical condition is not good. The basic nature of housewives is to engage them in taking care of their family and children's and lack of concentration towards their health. So this is also a causative factor of sweta pradar.

Discussion on observation on disease profile

History of present illness: In this study 80% patients were gradual onset; while 20% were sudden onset of the chief complaint. Malnutrition occurs gradually and if stay prolonged leads to suppressed immunity which is one of the cause for vaginal discharge.

History of past illness: In the present study we found that maximum 16.66% patients had past medical history. Any type of past illness more prone to produces new disease.

History of drug administration (past treatment): Maximum number of patients 13.33% had history of consuming modern medicine while 3.33% were having history of use Ayurvedic drugs. Hence most of the patients come to after treated by many doctors.

Family history: In the present history we found that in 83.33% of patients family history was absent while 16.66% of patients family history was present. From this data we cannot be concluded that family history is one of the reasons for sweta pradar.

Personal history

- **Aaharaj nidan:** In the present history we found that maximum 71.66% were vegetarian while 28.33% were having mixed diet. In the present study regarding dominant rasa in diet, madhur and lavan, amla, katu, rasa dominancy was present in 31.66%, 25%, 18.33% & 16.66% respectively. Excessive intake of this type of rasa dominancy in diet aggravates dosas (tridosh) which may be the most

important cause of sweta pradar. In the present study 30% of patients were having poor appetite, 28.33% of patients were having mandagni, and 18.33% patients were having vishamagni, 21.66% & 16.66% were having mridu and krura koshttha respectively. Abhisyandi ahara, adhyasana and viruddha ahara was present in 33.33%, 20% and 36.66% of patients respectively. Poor appetite, visham agni, mandagni, abhisyandi ahara, adhyasana and viruddha ahara etc. provokes the vitiation of tridosha in body, that leads to agnimandya and produce the ama. These are the major probable cause of sweta pradar.

- **Viharaj nidan:** Addiction study maximum 83.33% was habituated to tea, 5% were habituated to coffee and 1.66% patients were habituated to tobacco.

Nidra: In the present study 28.33 of patients were having alpa nidra and 11.66 were having diwaswapna which is a factor increasing kapha which are the major key factor of the pathogenesis of sweta pradar.

Emotional makeup: Regarding mansika hetu tensive in 16.66%, jolly in 11.66% of cases. It is mentioned in ayurvedic classics that vitiation of mansika doshas may interfere with the normal function of jatharagni leading to agnimandya and thus forming ama, which is the root cause for all the disease.

Discussion on vartaman rajjovruta (Menstrual history): 58.33% had onset of menarche at 13-15 years, 33.33 patients at (10-12) years, the data shows that most of the patients enrolled the study had normal age (13-15 years) for onset of menarche. In the present study we found that maximum of patients 84% were having regular menstrual cycle. 66% patients had moderate amount of blood loss, 22% of patients had scanty amount of menstrual blood loss.

Dymenorrhoea and character of menstrual flow: 30% patients had pain during menstruation. The data reveals that normal statement and probable cause could not be made.

Discussion on prasav vrutta

Parity and delivery wise: In the present study 83.33% of patients were parous while 16.66% of patients were nulliparous and 65% of patients were having full term normal delivery. While 18.33% of patients was having lscs.

Sexual history: In the present study it was found that maximum 98.33% patients were sexually satisfied and remaining 1.66% patients were having the complaints of sexually unsatisfied and 21.66% patients were having the complaints of dyspareunia.

Use of contraceptive devices: 41.66% were not using any type of contraceptive devices, while 15% of the patients had undergone tubal ligation. 26.66% of the patients were using condoms. From this data we cannot

be concluded that contraceptive history is one of the reasons for Sweta Pradar.

Discussion on gynecological examination

- 1. Per Vaginal examination:** According to per vaginal examination 100% patients were have normal vagina. On the basis of cervical examination 100% patients had firm. And according to Adnexae examination 100% patients had free adnexae.
- 2. Per Speculum examination:** On the basis of per speculum examination among 60 patients, maximum patients 100% had normal vagina. Among 60 patients, maximum patients 86.66% normal cervix on p/s examination, 13.33% patients had erosion in cervix on p/s examination.

Discussion on Pap smear examination: 26.66% patients had Negative for malignancy, 1.66% patients had acute purulent smear, 6.66% patients had Acute inflammatory smear, 1.66% patients had Acute inflammatory smear Negative for malignancy, 18.33% patients had Bacterial vaginosis, 41.66% patients had inflammatory smear, and 3.33% patients Atrophic inflammatory smear.

Discussion on mukhya vyadhi vrutta (Chief complaint)

- 1. Yonigata shweta/pitabh srav:** Maximum number of patients i.e. 26.66% had Jaliya Yonigata Shweta srava, 58.33% of the patients had Pichchila, 13.33% patients had Dadhivata, 1.66% patients had Pooybha Yonigata Shweta srava. Majuphala contains alkaloid tannic acid which is used to stop bleeding, chronic diarrhoea, etc. it is also use per vagina for douching purpose, the above shows the statistic purpose of tannic acid.
- 2. Associated complaints:** 51.66% patients had Yonikandu, 28.33% patients had Yonidurgandha, and where as Yoni Vedna were found in 13.33% of patients. It indicates this is not physiological discharge because normal vaginal discharge never causes pruritis and is not offensive too. So these yonigata lakshana signifying association of pathology.

85% patients had been suffering from Katishoola, 61.66% were suffering from Daurbalyata, and 68.33% patients were suffering from Adho-udar Vedna, 20% patients were suffering from Yonidaha. As described earlier, Shweta Pradar is Kapha- Vata predominant Tridoshaja Vyadhi. These entire symptoms may be due to the insufficient intake of nutritional food and some psychological factors like anxiety, depression etc. (Ahitkar ahar and Vihara), which are also causative factors of abnormal vaginal discharge. Our study also reveals the same thing.

All Symptoms specify Kapha, vata & Pitta Dosha involvement, because Yoni Srava and Kandu indicate the involvement of vitiated Kapha dosh; Yoni Vedna

indicates the involvement of Vitiated Vata Dosha; Yoni Durgandhya & Yoni Daha indicates the involvement of vitiated Pitta Dosha.

DISCUSSION ON EFFECT OF THERAPY (RESULT)

1. On pratyatm lakshan

Yonigata excessive Shwet/ Pitabha srav: Regarding the yonigata excessive sweta srava, extremely significant result ($p < 0.0001$) was observed in Group A and extremely significant in Group B ($p < 0.0001$). The comparative data is statistically is Not-Significant ($p > 0.9999$). The Drug Group A showed better percentage of relief in yonigata srava 86.0026% when compared with Group B- 78.5714%. It means the Drug given in Group A is more effective in reducing yonirava than group B.

Majuphal: It may be due to sweta pradar is kapha vata predominance tridosaja vyadhi and the drug given in group A (Majuphala) also has tridosa shamak specially kapha pitta dosa shamak properties. Katu vipaka and sheeta veerya having the properties of deepan pachan kapha – kledahara and stambhan karma.

Kankola: It has kaphavata shamak property, katu and tikta rasa of kankola having the properties of deepan pachan, kapha kleda hara by which it digest amarasa and reduces the excessive production of kapha and removes the obstruction of srotus and pacify vitiated kapha & kleda and diminishes the srava.

❖ Majuphal showed better percentage of relief as compared to Kankol it may be due to Kashaya Rasa Sheet veerya, Stambhak, Wound-healing, anti-inflammatory, anti bacterial, analgesic, properties by which it kill causative micro-organism and cure the Shwetapradara.

On associated symptoms

Yonikandu: Regarding the yonikandu, extremely significant result ($p = 0.0002$) was observed in Group A and extremely significant in Group B ($p = 0.0005$). The comparative data is statistically is Not-Significant ($p > 0.9999$). The Drug Group A showed better percentage of relief in yonikandu 78.941% when compared with Group B- 68.422%. It means the Drug given in Group A is more effective in reducing yonikandu than group B.

The significant result may be possible as kandu is the lakshan of vitiated kapha dosa and both drug majuphala and kankola having laghu guna by which it act as kaphahara property and clears the channels of the body (srotosodhana). According to API, AV etc. and katu, tikta rasa of kankola having kandughna & krimighna property so direct inhibit the growth of krimi and finally helps in diminishes kandu.

❖ Majuphal Showed better percentage in Yonikandu as compared to Kankol, It may be due to Kaphashamak, larvicidal anti-bacterial properties.

Yonidurgandha: Regarding the yonidurgandha vary significant result ($p=0.0039$) was observed in Group A and only significant in Group B ($p=0.0313$). The comparative data is statistically is Not-Significant ($p>0.9999$). The Drug Group A showed better percentage of relief in yonidurgandh 92.311% when compared with Group B- 75.007%. It means the Drug given in Group A is more effective in reducing yonidurgandh than group B. it may be due to the sheeta veerya property of majuphala which normalize the vitiated pitta and reduces yonidaurgandha and kankola is a sugandhita dravya and has a property of daurgandha nasak which diminishes the yonidaurgandha.

Yonivedna: Regarding the yonivedana, non significant result ($p=0.2500$) was observed in Group A and non significant in Group B ($p>0.9999$). The comparative data is statistically is Not quit Significant ($p>0.0556$). The Drug Group A showed better percentage of relief in yonivedana 50.017% when compared with Group B- 20.040%. It means the Drug given in Group A is more effective in reducing yonivedana than group B. it may be due to the vatashamak and usnaveerya property of kankola and balya & vatashamak property of majuphala (R.N.) which reduces the yonivedana.

Katishool: Regarding the katishool, vary significant result ($p=0.0039$) was observed in Group A and extremely significant in Group B ($p=0.0010$). The comparative data is statistically is Not-Significant ($p=0.4206$). The Drug Group A showed better percentage of relief in katishool 37.924% when compared with Group B- 28.22%. It means the Drug given in Group A is more effective in reducing katishool than group B. katishool is lakshan of vatadusti and trial drug kankola has ushna veerya and shoolnasak property according to API and majuphal has vatashamak property (R.N.) which diminishes katishoola.

Daurbalya: Regarding the daurbalya, non significant result ($p=0.1250$) was observed in Group A and non significant in Group B ($p=0.1250$). The comparative data is statistically is Not-Significant ($p>0.9999$). The Drug Group B showed better percentage of relief in daurbalya 18.184% when compared with Group A- 15.388%. It means the Drug given in Group B is more effective in reducing daurbalya than group A. it may be due to the trial drug majuphala has balya property and kankola has katu, tikta rasa, ushna veerya which is having deepan pachan property by which it stimulate agni, increase digestive power which digest amarasa and remove the obstruction of srotus by which it act as dhatuposhan which reduce daurbalya.

Adhудар vedna: Regarding the adho-udar vedana, vary significant result ($p=0.0078$) was observed in Group A and extremely significant in Group B ($p=0.0010$). The comparative data is statistically is Not-Significant ($p=0.4206$). The Drug Group A showed better percentage of relief in adho-udar vedana 50.006% when compared

with Group B- 45.147%. It means the Drug given in Group A is more effective in reducing adho-udar vedana than group B. it may be due to the kankola has shoolnasak property.

Yonidah: Regarding the yoni daha, non significant result ($p=0.0625$) was observed in Group A and non significant in Group B ($p=0.2500$). The comparative data is statistically is Not-Significant ($p>0.9999$). The Drug Group B showed better percentage of relief in yoni daha 66.68% when compared with Group A-62.513%. It means the Drug given in Group B is more effective in reducing yoni daha than group A. majuphala has sheet veerya property which normalize vikrit pitta and katu, tikta rasa of kankola having daha prashaman property which reduces yonidah.

Discussion on effect of therapy of laboratory parameters

- 1. On hemoglobin %:** Regarding the Hb% very significant ($p=0.0077$) was observed in Group A and Non significant in Group B ($p=0.1701$). The comparative data is statistically is Not-Significant ($p=0.9579$). The Drug Group A showed better percentage of relief in Hb % 8.114 when compared with Group B 1.9771%. It means the Drug given in Group A is better than Group B to increase Hb%.
 - ❖ It may be due to drug have the property of Balvardhak, Dhatuposhan karma.
- 2. On ESR:** Regarding ESR, Extremely Significant ($p=0.0001$) was observed in group A and Not-Significant in Group B ($p=0.3984$). The comparative data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.7838$). It means the drug given to both group are statistically equally effective. Majuphal showed better percentage of relief as compared to Kankol. In maximum patients ESR came to normal range in group A it might be due to the anti inflammatory and antibacterial property of majuphala. In Group B, ESR came to normal range in some patients it may be due to krimighna property of kankola.
- 3. TLC:** Regarding TLC, Not-Significant ($p=0.3979$) was observed in group A and Not-Significant in Group B ($p=0.2505$). The comparative data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.9304$). It means the drug given to both group are statistically equally effective.
- 4. DLC**
 - **Neutrophils:** Regarding Neutrophills, Not Significant result ($p=0.0517$) was observed in group A and Not-Significant in Group B ($p=0.4134$). The comparative data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.9162$). It means the drug given to both group are statistically equally effective.
 - **Lymphocyte:** Regarding Lymphocyte, Significant result ($p=0.0284$) was observed in group A and Not-Significant in Group B ($p=0.2561$). The comparative

data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.9619$). It means the drug given to both group are statistically equally effective.

- **Monocyte:** Regarding Monocyte, Very Significant result ($p=0.0034$) was observed in group A and Not-Significant in Group B ($p=0.8399$). The comparative data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.6496$). It means the drug given to both group are statistically equally effective.
- **Basophil:** Regarding Basophil, Not Significant result ($p=0.00$) was observed in group A and Not-Significant in Group B ($p=0.00$). The comparative data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.00$).
- **Eosinophil:** Regarding eosinophils, Not Significant result ($p=0.0011$) was observed in group A and Not-Significant in Group B ($p=0.3796$). The comparative data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.5835$). It means the drug given to both group are statistically equally effective.

Discussion on effect of trial drug on wet vaginal smear test (Microscopic examination)

- **On Trichomona vaginalis:** Regarding the Trichomona vaginalis, Not Significant result ($p=0.1610$) was observed in group A and Not-Significant in Group B ($p=0.1853$). The comparative data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.4696$). It means the drug given to both group are statistically equally effective.
- **On Candida albicans:** Not Significant result ($p=0.1610$) was observed in group A and Not-Significant in Group B ($p=0.0808$). The comparative data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.3516$). It means the drug given to both group are statistically equally effective Regarding the Candida albicans. Here the cause of non significant result is due to very small sample size i.e. only 4 patients out of 30 were having trichomonas infection and only 4 patients out of 30 were having candida albicans infection, they all got equal relief with Group A and Group B.
- **Bacteria:** Regarding the Bacteria, Extremely Significant result ($p=0.0002$) was observed in group A and Significant in Group B ($p=0.0158$). The comparative data is statistically Significant ($p=0.038$). It means the drug given to group A is statistically more effective than Group B. It may be due to the majuphala having anti bacterial property.
- **Pus cells:** Regarding the Pus cells, Extremely Significant result ($p<0.0001$) was observed in group A and Extremely Significant in Group B ($p=0.0001$). The comparative data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.8709$). It means the drug given to both group are statistically equally effective.
- **Epithelial:** Regarding the epithelial, Extremely Significant result ($p<0.0001$) was observed in group A and Extremely Significant in Group B ($p<0.0001$). The comparative data is statistically Not-Significant ($p=0.8546$). It means the drug given to both group are statistically equally effective. The drug is equally

effective in normalise the pus cells and epithelial cells as both drug having antibacterial, antiprotozoal, antimicrobial, vishagna, vranropan property.

- Significant results in subjective and objective parameter may be due to the vranropana, vishagna, deepan, pachan, agnimandyahara, anti inflammatory, antibacterial, anticarcinogenic, larvicidal, wound healing, analgesic properties of majuphala.
- The trial drug Kankol also poses property of krimighna, Daurgandhyahara, Tridoshahara, Sugandhikara, Bastishodhan Mutravirechaniya, and Hrudya etc and antimicrobial, antioxidant, antifungal, antibacterial property.^[4]
- Effect of therapy in all subjective parameters in group A showed extremely significant result in *yonisrava* and *yonikandu* and very significant result in *yonidaurgandha*, *katishool*, and *adho-udar vedana* and non significant result in *yonidaah & daurbalya*.
- Group B showed extremely significant result in *yonisrava*, *yonikandu*, *katishool* and *adho-udar vedana* and non significant result in *yonivedana* and *yonidaha*.
- Effect of therapy in all objective parameters in group A showed extremely significant result in ESR, puss cells, epithelial cells, bacteria and very significant result in Hb%, monocyte, eosinophils, and non significant result in TLC, neutrophils, candida albicans and trichomonas vaginalis.
- Group B showed extremely significant result on puss cells, epithelial cells, and significant result in bacteria and non significant results in TLC, ESR, DLC, trichomonas vaginalis and candida albicans.

Percentage of relief

- In group A and Group B percentage of relief 86.0026% and 78.57% in *yonisrava* and 78.94% & 68.422% in *yonikandu* and 92.311% & 75.007% in *yonidurgandha* were found respectively.

Overall improvement status

- In group A showed Maximum number of patients (39.28) had moderate improvement, 21.42% patients had marked improvement and 17.85 & 17.85 had mild improvement and unchanged respectively, 3.57% patients had complete remission. In Group B 33.33% & 29.16% patients had mild and moderate improvement respectively, 16 % had marked improvement and 12.50% patients had complete remission, remaining 8.33% patients had unchanged.
- From the above data concluded that the trial drug treated in group A showed better result in all subjective and objective parameter than group B. Hence the group A is more effective then group B.
- During the clinical trial no adverse effect of the drug was observed in any of the patients. So the present study supports the use of *Majuphala* and *Kankola* in the management of *Sweta pradar (Leucorrhoea)*.

Probable mode of action

- The drug *Majuphal* having pharmacological properties such as *Kashaya Rasa*, *Laghu Ruksh Guna*, *Katu Vipaka*, *Shita Virya*, and *Kaphapitta shaman* properties. *Karma - Sangrahi*, *raktstambhan*, *mukhrognasak Vatahar*, *sankochak*, *keshkrishnikaran*, *balya vranropan*, *stambhan*, *sonitsthapan*, *yonisankochaka mutrastambhan deepan*, *grahi*; Actions by which drug act as *Shwetapradar Nashak*
- The drug *Kankol* having pharmacological properties such as *Katu Tikta Rasa*, *Laghu Ruksh Tikshna Guna*, *Katu Vipaka*, *Ushna Virya*, and *Kaphavata shaman* properties. *Karma – Daurgandhy nashana*, *Sugandhikara*, *Deepan Pachana Agnimandhya hara Ruchikar hrudya vishahar*, *Mutravirechaniya basti shodhan mukhrognasak*. Actions by which drug act as *Shwetapradar Nashak*.
- The drug *Quercus infectoria oliv* having analgesic, antibacterial, anticarcinogenic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, larvicidal and wound healing effects by which it help to cure sweta pradar.^[5]
- And the drug **Piper cubeba Linn** having Antimicrobial activity, Hepatoprotective activity, Antioxidant activity, Nephroprotective activity by which it help to cure sweta pradar.^[6]

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The present dissertation entitled “A Pharmaco-Clinical Study of *Majuphal* and *Kankol* W.S.R. to their effect on *Shweta Pradar*” was carried out with the aim of searching a better remedy to manage *swetapradar*.

In the first section a brief introduction is given in the beginning of dissertation which deals with general description, reason for the selection of drug and disease, aims and objectives, plan of study. It was a comparative study between *Majuphala churna* which was considered as group A and *kankola churna* which was considered as group B in which *Majuphala* was a control group in comparison of which effect of *kankola* churn on *sweta pradar* was studied. Clinical trial was conducted on total 60 patients, 30 in each group but 28 patients and 24 patients had completed the course of treatment in group A & B respectively.

The second section deals with conceptual study. The conceptual study is divided into two parts, firsts is drug profile and second is disease profile. First are the drug profile parts deals with the review of both drug *Majuphal* and *Kankola* with *ayurveda* and modern perspective. In this section historical background of the drug, the detailed description about name (synonyms and vernacular names), *Rupa* (morphological characters) and *Guna* (properties and therapeutic uses) along with its substitution and adulteration, chemical constituents, part used, doses, have been described. Second section is the disease review, under this historical background; ayurvedic review and modern review are covered.

In next section clinical study under this section observation and result have been summarized. Observation was done on all the criteria like age, religion, marital status, occupation, socio-economic status, *ahar vihar pareeksha*, subjective and objective parameters. Observations were analyzed and results were calculated on its basis. Results were tabulated and shown in graph and was correlated statistically with Wilcoxon Sign Rank test and Mann Whitney Test. In result of *yonisrava*; group A showed relief of 86.0026% where as group B showed relief of 78.57%. In results of objective parameters group A & B showed Hb% of 8.114 % and 1.977 % relief and 28.288% & 2.331% relief in ESR parameter respectively while puss cells showed 77.287% & 70.144% and epithelial cells showed 71.917% & 64.179% relief in Group A & B respectively.

In discussion section a complete discussion on each and every point was done and a probable mode of action of drug from *ayurveda* as well as modern point of view is discussed.

NOTE:- *Majuphal* showed better percentage of relief on some DLC parameter as compared to *Kankol*, this may be due to having property of *Jwarahna*, *Shwasahara*, *Kasahara*, *Vishaghana*, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial analgesic, larvicidal, wound healing and antioxidant property.

REFERENCE

1. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316999394_Ethnopharmacology_of_Quercus_infectoria_Galls_A_Review
2. <https://www.indianmedicinalplants.info/herbs/index.php/medicinal-plants-pictures-a-details/1156-kankola-piper-cubeba-medicinal-uses-and-pharmacology>
3. Md. Anzar Alam, Shamim Ahmed Review Article *www.ajphr.com* 2013, Volume 1, Issue 6 ISSN : 2321-3647(online)
4. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Cubebina#:~:text=It%20has%20a%20role%20as,cyclic%20acetal%20and%20a%20lactol>
5. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/215519175_Mazu_Quercus_infectoria_An_Overview
6. <https://www.indianmedicinalplants.info/herbs/index.php/medicinal-plants-pictures-a-details/1156-kankola-piper-cubeba-medicinal-uses-and-pharmacology>